

VAKA TAKDİMİ

CASE REPORT

NOT EVERY RENAL COLIC IS A REAL RENAL COLIC

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ABSTRACT

Renal colic presents with a transient, writhing, severe pain in the form of intermittent cramps, which is common in emergency services. In our case, we aimed to describe a case of subcapsular renal hematoma incidentally encountered in a young woman without any additional disease or trauma, who applied to the emergency department with the complaint of pain in the form of renal colic.

Case report: A 32-year-old young woman applied to the emergency service with the complaint of colic-like right flank pain that had been intermittent for 2 days. The patient, whose vital signs were stable, did not have any additional disease. We evaluated the patient with the first USG, who was not relieved by symptomatic treatment. During the examination with USG, we saw that there was a loculated collection area around the right kidney, this seemed suspicious to us in terms of a subcapsular hematoma or a septal cystic structure. Thereupon, we planned to perform a contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) scan. In the withdrawn CT; We observed that it is compatible with subcapsular hematoma with limited fluid density in the renal capsules in the perirenal planes on the right, and grade 2 hydronephrosis in the structures of the right kidney pelvicalyxial system. Our patient was hospitalized by the urology clinic for follow-up and treatment.

Conclusions: In our case, we wanted to share with you a case that we came across spontaneously, who was not exposed to any trauma, and was diagnosed quickly by USG. Thanks to this imaging that we applied to our patient for the first time, she was of great help in the diagnosis of subcapsular renal hematoma, which is rare. However, computed tomography was needed for definitive diagnosis.

Key Words: Renal colic, subcapsular renal hematoma, emergency medicine

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INTRODUCTION

Renal colic presents with a transient, writhing, severe pain in the form of intermittent cramps, which is common in emergency services. Classically, it is an uncomfortable condition that can be accompanied by costovertebral angle tenderness, flank pain, colic, and nausea and vomiting. Although renal colic is supported by clinical suspicion, many diagnoses can be confused with renal colic. In our case, we aimed to describe a case of subcapsular renal hematoma incidentally encountered in a young woman without any additional disease or trauma, who applied to the emergency department with the complaint of pain in the form of renal colic.

CASE REPORT

Case; A 32-year-old young woman applied to the emergency service with the complaint of colic-like right flank pain that had been intermittent for 2 days. On physical examination of the patient, right costovertebral pain sensitivity was present. no rebound-defense on abdominal examination and no ral-rhonchus in lung sounds. The patient, whose vital signs were stable, did not have any additional disease. Whole blood, biochemistry, urine and beta hcg tests were requested from the patient and symptomatic treatment was started at this time. In laboratory tests of the patient, WBC (White Blood Cell): 12.77 K/UL, HGB (Hemoglobin): 15g/dL, CRP (c-reactive protein): 4.4 mg/L, Creatinine: 0.98mg/dL, urea: 47 mg/dL, potassium: 4.56 mmol/L. WBC (White Blood Cell): 6.71 K/UL, HGB (Hemoglobin): 12.4 g/dL, CRP(c-reactive protein): 1.5 mg/L, Creatinine: 0.76 mg/dL, urea: 18.3 mg/dL, potassium: 4.56 mmol/L, beta hcg negative, and there was no significant feature in urinalysis. Mindray branded DC-60 model ultrasonography (USG) is available in the emergency department of our hospital. We evaluated the patient with the first USG, who was not relieved by symptomatic treatment. During the examination with USG, we saw that there was a loculated collection area around the right kidney, measuring approximately 85*45 mm in its widest part, and containing thin septa in places. This seemed suspicious to us in terms of a subcapsular hematoma or a septal cystic structure. Thereupon, we planned to perform a contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) scan after our patient had normal urea- creatinine values. In the withdrawn CT; We observed that it is compatible with subcapsular hematoma with limited fluid density in the renal capsules in the perirenal planes on the right, and grade 2 hydro-nephrosis in the structures of the right kidney pelvicalyxial system. Our patient was hospitalized by the urology clinic for follow-up and treatment.

Figure 1. Ultrasound images of the patient

Figure 2. Computerized tomography images of the patient

DISCUSSION

Renal colic is pain caused by increased pressure in the urinary system or usually caused by stones(1). Although renal colic originates from urolithiasis, different etiological causes may present with pain in the style of renal colic. The most serious of these are abdominal aortic aneurysm rupture and aortic dissection(2). After these 2 life-threatening causes, similar findings may occur in various renal, ureter, bladder, gastrointestinal, and gynecological causes.

The use of USG in emergency services has increased in recent years and has become an indispensable auxiliary diagnostic tool in daily practice. USG; It acts as a modern stethoscope for today's

emergency medicine physicians with its non-invasive, rapid and no radiation risk. There is Min-drain branded DC-60 model USG in Karaman Training and Research Hospital. We routinely use this USG very frequently.

Subcapsular hematomas, which we think to occur spontaneously, are rare. We have seen that the literature on the subject is sparse. However, in a study by Shinya Somiya et al., we see cases of subcapsular hematoma occurring as a complication after transurethral ureterolithotripsy(3). Or, in a study by Michael A. Kozmonski et al., it is believed to be associated with the risk of renal hematoma after extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy applied for kidney stones(4).

In our case, we wanted to share with you a case that we came across spontaneously, who was not exposed to any trauma, and was diagnosed quickly by USG. Thanks to this imaging that we applied to our patient for the first time, she was of great help in the diagnosis of subcapsular renal hematoma, which is rare. However, computed tomography was needed for definitive diagnosis.

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